

Rija Nagar (Cham New Year) Rituals

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Southeast Asian Religions, Language, Austronesian, Malayo-Polynesian, Malayo-Sumbawan, North and East Malayo-Sumbawan, Aceh-Chamic, Chamic, Coastal Chamic, Cham, Cham Religions

Annual celebration of the new year among Cham communities in Vietnam. This two-day experience happens during the first month of the year (according to the Cham calendar, the Sakawi), and incorporates a number of ritual practices and ceremonial events where religious dignitaries communicate between the spiritual realm and the broader community to expel bad and unlucky things, and ensure a positive, productive new year as the rainy season begins.

Date Range: 1600 CE - 2025 CE

Region: Cham Ahiér Communities

Region tags: South Central Coast, Ninh Thuận, Bình Thuận, Phú Yên, Khánh Hòa, Nha Trang (Aia Trang), Lam Đồng, Phan Rí (Parik), Phan Thiết (Hamâ Lithit), Asia, Vietnam, Southeast Asia, Phan Rang (Panrang)

This region that includes the locations, communities, and polities associated with the practices of the Cham Ahiér religion from 1600-2015 and beyond. It includes the old Champa regions of Pāṇḍuraṅga and Kauṭhara, along with the contemporary urban region of TP. Hồ Chí Minh. Pāṇḍuraṅga (centered on the temple-polity of Paṅrauṅ / Panrān, now Phan Rang) includes the contemporary province of Ninh Thuận, much of the lowlands of contemporary Lam Đồng, and even arguably with outposts in the vicinity of Biên Hòa/Đồng Nai. Kauṭhara includes both Phú Yên and Khánh Hòa provinces, especially the polity-port of Aia Trang (now Nha Trang) centered at the temple-polity of Yangpunagara. Most of historical Kauṭhara was annexed by the early seventeenth century. Most of historical Pāṇḍuraṅga was annexed by the early 19th century. The families of contemporary Cham Ahiér have lived predominantly in these regions for centuries, but may also be found in all of Vietnam's

provinces. Cham Ahiér communities are largest in Lam Đồng and Ninh Thuận provinces, but individuals still make regular pilgrimages to Yangpunagara/Aia Trang and points northward for both religious and cultural reasons. Prior to 2025, the region associated with the coast of Lam Đồng was called Bình Thuận.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

Site

Does the ritual take place in an outside setting?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Enclosed?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual events and worship practices take place within outdoor spaces, in community homes, at ceremonial houses (danaok), as well as in enclosed tent-like ceremonial structures, called the kajang. The kajang is a three-sided, temporary, tent-like structure, with an open front side oriented towards the east, which is a sacred spiritual direction. Other, more permanent, physical structures involved in Rija Nagar, such as community households or village-level ceremonial houses (e.g. the Danaok of Po Klaong Can in Palei Hamu Craok, or the Kalan of Po Nai in Palei Padra), will have their own idiosyncratic floorplan and material composition.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Elevated?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ By a body of water?

– No

Notes: Not necessarily. Some Cham villages will be closer in proximity to the coastline, and in those instances, Rija Nagar ceremonies will take place alongside the Champa Sea (or the South-China Sea as it is known today). However, for other villages further inland, there is nothing inherent to the ceremony itself taking place alongside a body of water aside from making prayer and sacrificial offerings towards the sea in the east, which is a sacred cardinal direction by which spirits travel. Among some Cham villages, the closing ceremony of Rija Nagar will take place next to a river, where the Salih (an effigy made from raw rice flour depicting two men and two women) will be sent downriver as a means to expel negative energy and misfortune, and welcome prosperity for the coming year.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Near fire (e.g., volcano, lava, human-made fire)?

– Yes

Notes: Fire is a central motif in many Rija Nagar ceremonial practices, and the most widely known involves spirit invocation where the Ka-ing will dance on top of a small human-made fire as others play ceremonial instruments. The iconic nature of this particular ritual practice has been widely recognized in local media and by tourism officials. There have been documented instances of attempts to implement the performance of this ritual at sacred-heritage sites like Po Klaong Girai temple-towers (see Quang, Noseworthy & Paulson 2022 for a case study), however local religious dignitaries responded negatively so as to preserve the sanctity of both the ritual itself (as performed properly during Rija Nagar), as well as the Po Klaong Girai temple-tower complex, which is not only a heritage destination for the Cham civilization, but also a living heritage site used by members of the community for religious events, ceremonies, and festivals.

Reference: Quang, Tuyen Dai, William Noseworthy, and Dave Paulson. "Rising Tensions: Heritage-tourism Development and the Commodification of "authentic" Culture Among the Cham Community of Vietnam". *Cogent Social Sciences* 8, no. 1 (August 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2022.2116161>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In a location considered holy?

– Yes

Notes: In instances where Rija Nagar ceremonial practices take place within the *kajang*, this specific structure is sacred, and only erected for the purposes of Rija Nagar. Within villages, many Rija Nagar ceremonies and practices will take place in ceremonial houses dedicated to locally venerated ancestors and kings from the history of the Cham civilization, such as the worship of Po Klaong Cang specifically in Palei Hamu Craok, or the veneration of Po Nai in Palei Padra. At the regional level, there is an understanding that the entire landscape of Cham villages themselves have a spiritual power and symbolic meaning according to Cham religious understandings and local history. (For a more detailed discussion on this topic, see: Schweyer, A. V. (2017). Potent places in Central Vietnam: 'Everything that comes out of the earth is Cham'. *The Asia Pacific Journal of Anthropology*, 18(5), 400-420.)

Reference: Schweyer, Anne-Valérie. "Potent Places in Central Vietnam: 'everything That Comes Out of the Earth Is Cham'" 18, no. 5 (October 20, 2017). <https://doi.org/10.1080/14442213.2017.1370478>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [Specify]

– N/A

Does the ritual take place in an inside setting?

– Yes

Notes: Rija Nagar practices begin in an enclosed tent-like structure known as a "*kajang*." In general, this approximately 8m x 5m structure will usually be made up to two roofs, and adorned with thatched walls on all sides except facing east—the direction of the spirits. On the ceiling of this ritual space, a white cloth is hung to symbolize the universe, called the "*Lâm linh*." Beneath it, opposite the cloth is a ritual object called the "*Muron*," which is also a white cloth tied to two posts. Three pillars at the front of the ritual house are wrapped in white cloth as well, and this sacred space is where Rija Nagar rituals first take place. (Sakaya 2003). Other inside settings will include ceremonial houses for specific Cham ancestors, such as the Danaok Po Klaong Can in Palei Hamu Craok, and the Kalan Po Nai in Palei Padra.

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

↳ Underground?

– No

↳ Is there an acknowledgment or reference to the elements or materials from which the setting is created? (e.g., wood or stone for a building)

– Yes

Notes: In the context of the kajang: The white cloths adorned on this structure have a symbolic meaning to denote the universe itself, and their particular arrangement facing the sacred east, are necessary to welcome spiritual ancestors and gods that participate in Rija Nagar events.

Is the ritual carried out in a public place?

– Yes

↳ Is the public space restricted in any way? (i.e. public, but only for specific members of the religious group?)

– Yes

Notes: Across Rija Nagar events, ceremonials, and rituals, the physical center of the ritual space is where Cham priests will perform prayers and ceremonial dances, while an outer periphery is for community participants to view and participate in the Rija Nagar ceremonies. While the arrangement of these inside-outside demarcations will vary depending on the structure itself (e.g. a temporary like the kajang ritual tent, or a more permanent household-like structure such as the Kalan Po Klaong Can), they often will have very salient boundaries indicated by the types of ritual activities taking place within them, as well as the specific ritual specialists (or community members) who occupy those spaces. This can be observed in many of the associated media files with this DRH entry, for example in the video and photos of Rija Nagar at the Danaok of Po Klaong Can. The ritual specialists performing music and offering prayer to the mukhalingum are seated directly in the center of the ceremonial house, while community participants who offer prayers and offerings sit nearby, but a bit further from the sacred center. General observers from the community, as well as outside visitors, will be on the outside of these two inner layers of participants in the Rija Nagar events celebrating the new year.

Is the ritual carried out in a private place?

– No

Is there a specific site or building associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Rija Nagar practices begin in an enclosed tent-like structure known as a "kajang." In general, this approximately 8m x 5m structure will usually be made up to two roofs, and adorned with thatched walls on all sides except facing east—the direction of the spirits. On the ceiling of this ritual house, a white cloth is

hung to symbolize the universe, called the “Lâm linh.” Beneath it, opposite the cloth is a ritual object called the “Muron,” which is also a white cloth tied to two posts. Three pillars at the front of the ritual house are wrapped in white cloth as well, and this sacred space is where Rija Nagar rituals first take place. (Sakaya 2003). In addition, there are many other village-specific buildings that are constructed for the specific veneration of particular Cham ancestors, deities, and royal figures. For example, in Palei Hamu Craok, there is a permanent structure venerating the sacred Cham ancestor Po Klaong Can, a contemporary and friend of the famous Po Klaong Girari. These permanent structures will be built, and used for ritual purposes, according to the specific traditions and history of each respective village. These permanent structures venerating specific historical and ancestral individuals are not solely utilized during Rija Nagar, but rather, are part of every annual type of religious and ceremonial celebration in the Cham community (e.g. the Danaok of Po Kalong Can is used not only during Rija Nagar, but other yearly events like the Katé Festival).

Is the site associated with this ritual considered sacred?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the sacred orientation of the kajang structure accords with a cosmological orientation to the east, which is a sacred direction from which spirits arrive (Sakaya 2003).

Was the site associated with this ritual created?

– Yes

↳ Was it temporary?

– Yes

Notes: These structures are erected at the start of the Rija Nagar ceremony, and disassembled afterwards.

↳ Was it permanent?

– No

Was the site associated with this ritual found?

– No

Is the site associated with a metaphysical concept?

– Yes

Notes: Metaphysical in that constituent parts denote the universe itself, and the orientation of the kajang

accords with sacred cardinal directions, principally the east, from which all spirits arrive.

Is the site representative of another physical or metaphysical space?

– No

Is the site oriented to the sun, stars, or other astronomical features?

– Yes

Notes: In general, many religious structures and sites in the Cham community are constructed in relation to the east, which is a sacred cardinal direction by which spirits travel. Some like the kajang (temporary tent-like structure) during Rija Nagar have an opening towards the east (and walls on the other three sides), which allows the Ka-ing ritual practitioner to give prayers, make offerings, and perform ceremonies directed towards the east as necessary to fulfill their role as a mediator between the spiritual realm and the community at-large. Other, more-permanent, sacred structures like the Po Klaong Girai temple-tower complex have also been constructed in reference to the sacred east, where the main door of the temple-tower's central Kalan faces east as well.

Does the site have a particular directional orientation (e.g., N, S, E, W)?

– Yes

Notes: East.

Is the site oriented to landforms (e.g., mountains, rivers, coast, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: From the perspective of coastal Vietnam, the eastern orientation is faced toward the coastline of the contemporary South China Sea, historically known as the Champa Sea to indigenous communities in Vietnam. Opposite this direction are the Trường Sơn mountains, behind which the sun sets, and is encoded in aspects of the Cham language, such as in the phrase for 'sunset:' aia harei trun cek (lit. 'the sun falls behind the mountain').

Frequency

How often is this ritual performed?

– Yes

↳ Annually:

– Yes

Notes: Held during the first month of the year according to the Cham Sakawi Ahiér (Lunar Calendar). Historically, the Rija Nagar ritual was brought to the civilization of Champa during the 17th century, during the reign of Po Romé. The term “Rija” itself has been given a number of different interpretations over the years. Among the earliest appearances in scholastic literature comes from Aymonier who, during his compilation of a Cham-French dictionary in 1906, associated this term with the Sanskrit term, “Raja,” literally meaning ‘magic, spirit possession,’ but in cultural context denoting kings, royalty, and royal dance ceremonies. Later scholars would define this term in similar manners, like Moussay defining it as a ‘dance ritual.’ Others point to different etymological origins, such as the Ban Biên Soạn Sách Chữ Chẵm (Cham Language Textbook Editorial Board) that connects it to the Sanskrit term “Raya,” meaning ‘festival.’ Nevertheless, Sakaya maintains that the interpretation of Rija/Raja denoting ‘king’ or ‘royalty’ may be the most reliable as the very earliest historical instances Rija rituals held them exclusively in royal contexts, and only later, after the decline of the Champa civilization, was practice of Rija extended beyond royal courts into more local contexts like villages. Rija, as a general term, denotes the broader system of folk-religious rituals conducted by the Cham community that incorporate elements of magic and spirit possession among shamanistic priests, where royal kings and ancestral spirits are venerated in ceremonial practice. Rija Harei (daytime ritual) has been documented in historical records before the 15th century during the reign of Po Klaong Girai. Rija Nagar appears later after the 15th century, at a time when Champa was intimately connected to the Malay world via strong diplomatic relations, and experienced various global influences from Islam. This historical connection between Champa and the Malay world appears in the structure of Rija Nagar events, particularly on the first day where Cham deities associated with Islamic origins - Yang Biruw, or new gods - are venerated. Other Rija events furthermore reflect historical connections between Champa and the Malay courts, particularly Rija Praong, which is the largest and most elaborate of the four different types of Rija practiced by the Cham community. Geographically, Rija Nagar is practiced by Cham populations living in the area traditionally known as Panduranga (and today indicates the southern portions of Lâm Đồng and Khánh Hòa provinces). This geographic distribution reflects the history of the Cham people as Panduranga is recognized as the last major mandala of influence from the Champa civilization, which lasted until 1832. Today Rija Nagar is still practiced annually in local Cham villages to ensure that the new year will be positive and productive for the community.

Reference: Truong, Van Mon. “Hệ Thống Lễ Raja Champa”. In Văn Hóa - Lịch Sử Champa [III]: Mối Quan Hệ Giữa Champa Và Thế Giới Mã Lai. Nhà Xuất bản ĐH Quốc Gia TP.HCM, 2024.

↳ Daily:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general)

populace)

↳ Weekly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Seasonally:

– Yes

Notes: Held to mark the transition from the dry season to the rainy season each year. This time period marks the start of the new year according to the Cham Sakawi Ahiér (Lunar Calendar), and is ecologically signaled by the oncoming moonsoon-season thunderstorms.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Once in an individual's lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Special events/occasions:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ During life cycle events (marriage, birth, death, etc.):

– No

Notes: Rija Nagar is not coordinated in reference to specific life-cycle events, however, at times,

there may be members of the community who organize life-cycle events like marriages, or a new house-warming event, in reference to the general timeframe of new-year celebrations.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Ad hoc:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the duration of the ritual unspecified?

– No

Notes: Rija Nagar is generally held among the Cham Ahiér during Wednesday and Thursday, while the Cham Awal will celebrate during Friday and Saturday, both of which falling on odd-numbered days of the first month of the year (Sakaya 2003:77).

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the duration of the ritual specified? (If so, include the range of duration in hours)

– Yes: 48

Notes: Typically, Rija Nagar is held over the period of two days; usually falling on the first Wednesday and Thursday of the new year among Cham Ahiér communities, or Thursday and Friday among Cham Awal communities. (Sakaya 2003:77; Thanh 2014:21). This two-day organization is described as 'one day entering and one day leaving' (entering on Thursday, leaving on Friday – tamâ di jip tabiak di suk). The first day, 'entering,' incorporates veneration for 'new' Islamic gods, while the second day, 'leaving' is dedicated to 'older' Brahmanic gods and ancestors. The phrase "tamâ Po biruw tabiak Po aklak" (the entering day offers to the new deity – the Islamic deity – and the leaving day offers to the old deity – the Brahminic deity) encapsulates this balance (Sakaya 2003). In addition, each day will be composed of specific ritual events and ceremonial practices depending on which gods, spirits and ancestors are being worshipped. For example, offerings of chicken are made on the first, 'entering' day, while offerings of goat are made during the second, 'leaving' day. The overall structure of Rija Nagar, in this way, represents one of the many

important symbolic dualisms in Cham cultural and religious history (such as the dual-structure and interdependent nature of the Ahiér (Brahminic-influenced) and Awal (Islamic-influenced) communities.

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

Reference: Thanh, Phan. “Bảo Tồn Và Phát Huy Nét Đẹp Văn Hóa Truyền Thông Qua Lễ Tục Ew Muk Kei, Lễ Hội Katé-ramawan Và Lễ Hội Rija Nagar”. In *Những Vấn Đề Văn Hóa-xã Hội Người Chăm Ngày Nay*, 5-31.. Tp. Hồ Chí Minh: Nxb. Trẻ, 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Participants

Are there agent(s) involved in this ritual?

def: this includes the enactor(s) of the ritual and/or entity or entities responsible for the efficacy of the ritual

– Yes

Notes: There are least 5 primary types of ritual officiants, with varied number of individuals working to fulfill each these roles. There may be instances of variation in the specific amount based on local availability and/or the number of dignitaries and musical specialists within a community. The primary types of ritual officiants required for Rija Nagar ceremonial events include: 1. Ka-ing: a spirit-medium priest who wears a red-colored ritual outfit, gets enacted in spiritual trances, and performs ceremonial dances over (symbolic) open flames. He works to convey the wishes of the community to the spiritual realm, and vice-versa. 2. Maduen: priests wearing ceremonial white robes tasked with playing the baranâng drum, singing the sacred hymns of the deities, and usually organized in groups of three with 1 principal singer and 2 assisting ritualists. 3. One musical specialist playing the small, high-pitched Saranai pipe-trumpet during ritual ceremonies. 4. At least two musical specialists playing the low-tone, dual-sided gineng drum (sometimes written as 'ginang') 5. Po Gru (or Imam), who is responsible for opening the ceremony and offering prayers to Po Awluah;

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

Reference: Thanh, Phan. “Bảo Tồn Và Phát Huy Nét Đẹp Văn Hóa Truyền Thông Qua Lễ Tục Ew Muk Kei, Lễ Hội Katé-ramawan Và Lễ Hội Rija Nagar”. In *Những Vấn Đề Văn Hóa-xã Hội Người Chăm Ngày Nay*, 5-31.. Tp. Hồ Chí Minh: Nxb. Trẻ, 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ How many agents are involved in this ritual?

– Yes: 5

Notes: This number reflects the types of agents who are a central part of all Rija Nagar ritual events. Nevertheless, across villages, there will be further agents involved depending on the ritual itself. For example, in venerating Po Nai at some villages, the Muk Rija (elder female spirit-medium dancer) will perform a dance to the sound of Cham instruments as she undergoes a spirit-possession trance. Other variations can be found in villages like Bình Nghĩa, which practices antiphonal singing and fertility dances that are not customary to other villages during Rija Nagar. Bình Nghĩa is furthermore unique in the presence of a Camanei, or a guardian of the temple, who in the past, before the presence of the Ka-ing, substituted for the ritual dancer in ceremonies. For further discussion on the distinctiveness of Bình Nghĩa Rija Nagar ceremonies, see Diễm & Hương (2025).

Reference: Diễm, T. C. T., and L. Hương. "Cấu Trúc Luồng Hợp Trong Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm (nghiên Cứu Trường Hợp Lễ Rija Nagar-Lễ Hội Đầu Năm Của Người Chăm Tỉnh Ninh Thuận)". *Tạp Chí Văn Hóa Nghệ Thuật*, no. 599 (2025): 46-50..

↳ Are agents of specific gender/sex for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they male:

– Yes

↳ Are they female:

– No

↳ Are they transgender:

– No

↳ Are they non-binary:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– No

↳ What is the age range of agents in this ritual?

– Specify: 18-85

Notes: Generally, individuals who attain dignitary status will do so in adulthood, and maintain those roles in the religious life of the community throughout their life until they are elderly and psychically no longer able to do so.

- ↳ Do agents have to have biological distinctiveness for this ritual?
(e.g., twin, born breach, albino, mental illness, hermaphrodite, blind, other disability)
– No

- ↳ Do agents have to have a specific social role for this ritual?
(e.g., widow, unmarried, etc.)
– Yes
Notes: Their specific social roles are determined according to which type of dignitary they have become.

- ↳ Are agents required to be insiders for this ritual?
– Yes

- ↳ Are agents initiated?
– Yes
Notes: Each type of religious dignitary will have its own process of spiritual socialization, associated rituals, and initiation events.

- ↳ Are agents part of the social group?
– Yes
Notes: Religious dignitaries come from the local villages where they practice their spirituality.

- ↳ Other:
– N/A

- ↳ Are agents required to be outsiders for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are agents required to be specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Each dignitary is a specialist in their own role. The Maduen, for example, is someone with expertise not only in the structure, organization, and implementation of ritual events, but also the baranâng drum, which is used to direct ritual segments throughout Rija Nagar.

↳ Are agents non-specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for agents in this ritual?

(e.g., menstruating women, men of a certain age)

– Gender: Each of these three agents roles are fulfilled by male members of the community. Both male and female spectator participants in Rija Nagar include community members who offer prayers to ancestral spirits throughout the course of Rija Nagar events.

– Religious affiliation or status: Must be a religious dignitary within the Cham community.

↳ Are there supernatural agents associated with this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

Definition: humans who have undergone deliberate efforts to change/refine/develop/transform themselves.

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are there patient(s) involved in this ritual?

Definition: recipient, beneficiary, client, target, victim of ritual

– No

Are there participants other than the agent involved in this ritual?

Definition: besides the agent, other actively participating in ritual, by responding, singing, dancing, interacting with ritual agents

– Yes

Notes: Among all Rija ceremonies in the Cham community, Rija Nagar is distinct in that it is the only one connected to the entire village, whereas others like Rija Praong, Rija Harei, and Rija Dayup are celebrated in the home. In this way, community members in different villages participate in that they help to maintain their own village-specific customs and practices enacted during the annual Rija Nagar event. For example, certain villages who have ties to specific Cham gods and goddesses will organize practices to venerate those specific individuals, such as Po Inâ Nagar, the Mother Goddess of Champa. While there are principal agents in Rija Nagar who orchestrate specific performances and ritual devotions, the community, at-large, is also responsible for the maintenance of distinct, and varied, Rija Nagar traditions according to the

heritage traditions of their respective villages and hamlets.

↳ How many participants are involved in this ritual?
– Specify: Varied, depending on the size of the village community.

↳ The participants' gender/sex is:
– Yes

↳ Male:
– Yes

↳ Female:
– Yes

↳ Transgender:
– I Don't Know

↳ Non-binary:
– I Don't Know

↳ Other:
– N/A

↳ What is the age range of participants in this ritual?
– Specify: All age ranges relative to the demographics of the village population.

↳ Do participants have a specific social role for this ritual?
– No

↳ Are participants required to be insiders for this ritual?

– No

Notes: Mixed-marriage practices where Cham community members start families with outsiders (for example, with ethnic Kinh Vietnamese, or with foreigners from other countries) make it so that there is highly varied demographic compositions within and across Cham villages of Vietnam. As such, they, too, are members of the local village or hamlet community, and, as a result, are one of the intended recipients for the ritual benefits of the annual Rija Nagar.

↳ Are participants required to be outsiders for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants required to be specialists for this ritual?

– No

↳ Are participants non-specialists for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific prohibitions for participants to take part in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as participants in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ Are they ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Others:

– Yes [specify]: System of Spirits during Rija Nagar

Notes: In general, the Cham community worships a number of different gods and ancestral spirits in their religious practices. Many of these are shared among different villages, and certain spirits of individuals/historical figures/gods may be particularly important to specific villages (e.g. Palei Hamu Tranran that venerates Po Inâ Nagar). The respective village deity is worshipped first within this spiritual system. On the occasion of Rija Nagar, there are a number of Cham spirits that are venerated by the community: These may include specific individuals: Po Tang, Po Tang Ahok (the rowing deity), Po Gialau (the deity of agarwood and cinnamon), Cey Thun, Cey Dalim, Cey Haniim Par, Cey Sit, Cey Pruang (two princes), Po Garai Phauk, Po Dam (the young man), Po Riya (the deity of waves and the sea), Po Inâ Nagar (the Mother Goddess), Po Klaong Girai, Po Romé, Po Patao Bin Thor, Po Sah Inâ, Po Nai, Nai Bia Soi, Bia Kon, Bia Nun, Bia Than Can, Bia Than Cih. As well as elemental gods: Po Bhum (earth deities), Patau Aia (water deities), Aditiak (sun deities), Po Cek (mountain deities), Yang Tasik (sea deities), Po Yang Sri (rice deities).

Reference: Truong, Van Mon. "Hệ Thống Lễ Raja Champa". In Văn Hóa - Lịch Sử Champa [III]: Mối Quan Hệ Giữa Champa Và Thế Giới Mã Lai. Nhà Xuất bản ĐH Quốc Gia TP.HCM, 2024.

Are there spectators in this ritual?

Definition: not actively participating in ritual or required to perform any actions

– Yes

↳ How many spectators observe this ritual?

– Yes: 50

Notes: Exact numbers vary based on the size of the space where Rija Nagar rituals are held, as well as the number of visitors who attend from beyond the village.

↳ The spectators' gender/sex is:

– Yes

↳ Male:

– Yes

↳ Female:

– Yes

↳ Transgender:

– I Don't Know

↳ Non-binary:

– I Don't Know

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ What is the age range of spectators in this ritual?

– N/A

Notes: Open to the entire community within local villages, as well as outside visitors (such as

international and domestic tourist groups).

- ↳ Do spectators have a specific social role for this ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Are spectators required to be insiders for this ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Are spectators required to be outsiders for this ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Are spectators required to be specialists for this ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Are spectators non-specialists for this ritual?
 - No
- ↳ Are there specific prohibitions for spectators to take part in this ritual?
 - Yes [specify]: There are not specific behaviors or actions prohibited per-se, but rather, a respectful and quiet demeanor must be maintained while Rija Nagar rituals are performed.
- ↳ Are there supernatural beings that act as spectators in this ritual?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they deceased humans:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they ancestors:
 - Yes

↳ Are they non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ Are they abiotic or inorganic entities:

– No

↳ Are they divine/spiritual beings

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

Notes: An example of High God involvement in Rija Nagar would be Po Awluah, who is part of the ritual opening ceremonies led by the Po Gru (or Imam).

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Cham kings are spiritual ancestors that held positions of royal power throughout the history of the Cham civilization, and today are included across various ancestor-worship events within the religious life of the community.

↳ Are they transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– No

↳ Others:

– No

Cause/Trigger

Is this ritual practiced at will?

– Yes

↳ Is it individually determined:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it communally determined:

– Yes [specify]: Determined according to Cham Sakawi

Notes: The entire Rija Nagar (Cham New Year) ritual events are organized based on cultural traditions passed on for centuries, with commonalities across villages (such as the two-day structure, the types of offerings made on each day, etc.), and further variations existing within villages based on their worship of specific Cham ancestral figures, kings, and spirits. In this way, the community, at large, helps to determine the particularities of their Rija Nagar events, while specific religious dignitaries within the village thereafter enact these practices following a specific set of rituals and ceremonial practices over the course of two days.

Is participation obligatory?

– Yes

↳ Consequences of non-participation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Social ostracism

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Status loss

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Material/Physical punishment

– Yes

Notes: Material punishment in the form of bad seasonal harvests, leading to insufficient food resources for the community. One of the central themes of Rija Nagar shared among all Cham villages is to leave behind the dry season and pray for abundant rains with fruitful harvest. Accordingly, failure to conduct these ritual events may lead to material punishments in the shortage of crop yields, and the associated physical implications of insufficient food resources. In addition, material and physical punishments may occur as a result of failing to dispel unwanted and evil spirits from the village community.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishment

– Yes

Notes: Failure to properly venerate Cham ancestors, gods, and kings, will result in misfortunes returning to individuals, households, and villages. Even when Rija Nagar rituals are properly enacted, there are elements of punishment embedded within, such as when the Ka-ing spirit-medium priest communicates between ancestral gods and the community, and an assessment of the village is offered from the spirit realm. Sakaya (2003) notes, for example, practices in the veneration of Po Nai among some villages where an assessment will be made about the 'defiled' nature of the village itself, and the required rituals that must be performed to purify the village, protect the community, and bring favorable rains and winds.

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other

– Specify: Low productivity in seasonal harvests and welcomes subsequent spiritual

misfortunes for members of the Cham community.

Notes: In this way, Rija Nagar addresses the well-being of the village as a whole, from season to crops, to community members, to spiritual sanctity, each of these elements are intertwined and inexorably linked.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this ritual practiced as part of an event?

– Yes

Notes: Rija Nagar is one of four distinct types of Rija events in the Cham community. In addition to this annual new-year event, there is also Rija Praong, Rija Harei, and Rija Dayaup. Each type of Rija happens at a different time of year, and with its own set of ritual practices and ceremonial events. Nevertheless, Rija Nagar is distinguished among these four as the only Rija that is practiced at the village level (as opposed to the home), and shares structural and symbolic elements across Cham communities living throughout south-central Vietnam.

Is this ritual practiced as part of calendric or astrological causes/events?

– Yes

Notes: Held during the first month of the new year according to the Cham Sakawi, i.e. the Cham calendar. (Thanh 2014). Yasuko (2011:327) provides an example of a sample calendar, indicating when Rija Nagar occurs relative to other events throughout the year, as well as an interesting case study for the calibration of the calendar among different Cham villages. Importantly, Rija Nagar will happen over a two day period, falling on the first Wednesday and Thursday of the year among Cham Ahiér communities, or the first Thursday and Friday of the year among Cham Awal communities. In both cases, these will usually fall on odd-numbered days in the first month of the year (Sakaya 2003).

Reference: Yasuko, Yoshimoto. "Chapter 13: A Study of the Almanac of the Cham in South-central Vietnam". In *The Cham of Vietnam: History, Society and Art.*. Singapore: NUS Press, 2011. Phuong, T. K., & Lockhart, B. (Eds.).

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

Is this ritual triggered by hemerological considerations (system of favorable/unfavorable days)?

– Yes

Notes: The determination of favorable versus unfavorable days will be made by Cham religious dignitaries

who calculate the yearly calendar. Thereafter, the beginning and ending of Rija Nagar happening on specific days of the week is determined based on their favorable nature. For example, Wednesday is favorable in Cham Ahiér spiritual philosophy because it represents cosmic balance, and is therefore favorable for beginning Rija Nagar events.

Is the ritual practiced in response to seasonal change?

– Yes

Notes: Rija Nagar is a new-year ritual event signaling the changing weather patterns of the dry, drought-prone season to the cool, fresh rainy season (Thanh 2014:20). According to Sakaya, the Cham communities of Vietnam have a saying that: "Khi nghe tiếng sấm hướng đông, đông-tây Nhân dân đón hớn hử mọi điều yên tâm" (When hearing thunder in the east, east-west direction The people joyfully welcome all things with peace of mind) (2003:77).

Reference: Thanh, Phan. "Bảo Tồn Và Phát Huy Nét Đẹp Văn Hóa Truyền Thông Qua Lễ Tục Ew Muk Kei, Lễ Hội Katé-ramawan Và Lễ Hội Rija Nagar". In *Những Vấn Đề Văn Hóa-xã Hội Người Chăm Ngày Nay*, 5–31.. Tp. Hồ Chí Minh: Nxb. Trẻ, 2014.

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific natural events (e.g., drought, ecological death, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Changing seasonal patterns from the dry season to the wet, monsoon season in South-Central Vietnam.

Is the ritual practiced in response to specific social events (e.g., death of a leader, etc.)?

– No

Notes: While Rija Nagar is timed to mark the new year as the monsoon season begins, there are also social, spiritual, and interpersonal elements that are embedded in the organization of these ritual practices. For example, the calculation of the Cham Sakawi (Lunar-Solar Calendar) by Cham religious dignitaries is a social and spiritual process. For a case study on the calculation of the Cham calendar between Cham communities in South-Central Vietnam, see Yasuko (2011).

Reference: Yasuko, Yoshimoto. "Chapter 13: A Study of the Almanac of the Cham in South-central Vietnam". In *The Cham of Vietnam: History, Society and Art.*. Singapore: NUS Press, 2011. Phuong, T. K., & Lockhart, B. (Eds.).

Is the ritual performed in reaction to an ominous event?

– No

Is this ritual practiced during a specific life stage?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this ritual part of another ritual?

– No

Notes: Rija Nagar is related to the three other types of Rija events in the Cham community (Rija Praong, Rija Harei, and Rija Dayaup). But Rija Nagar itself is not a singular ritual, but rather a set of many different types of ritual and spiritual practices that are performed over the course of two days.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is this ritual financially sponsored by non-participants?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ By a government or ruling elite:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ By NGOs:

Definition: NGO: Non-profit organization

– Yes

Notes: If NGO support is available, it will often come from Cham-community NGOs abroad working towards the elimination of poverty via charity. There is nothing canonical or inherent about this

type of financial support, but rather circumstantial to the context of personal and professional relationships within the global Cham community.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ By clans or families:

– Yes [specify]: Clans and families from local villages.

Notes: Community members will make contributions to the Rija Nagar ritual events by means of small monetary donations, as well as food supplies for sacrifice and prayer as they are utilized by ritual practitioners throughout the two-day event.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ By particular individuals:

– Yes

Notes: International support often comes from international Cham diaspora communities living in the United States, France, Malaysia, and elsewhere.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other:

– N/A

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Purpose

Is the purpose of this ritual for maintenance?

– Yes

Notes: The Rija Nagar annual ritual offers maintenance in the areas of spiritual balance for the Cham community, productive harvest for food resources, and the maintenance of good fortune and prosperity for the upcoming year ahead. In the words of prominent Cham-studies scholars: "The purpose of the festival is to send off the old year, [and] welcome the new year; to commemorate ancestors who contributed to the village and its people; to drive away misfortunes from the past year; to pray for a peaceful new year, abundant health, favorable rainfall and gentle winds, bountiful harvests, year-round prosperity and happiness for all" (Thanh 2014:21). Sakaya notes that: "The Cham begin to organize the beginning-of-year festival Rija [Nagar] in order to generally dispel evil things and bad luck, so that in the new year they may receive things good for the villagers, and welcome water, pray for rain, prepare to begin the opening of canal-digging and rice cultivation" (2003:76). Taken together, the annual Rija Nagar serves a holistic purpose for maintenance of spiritual and communal balance, particularly in the domains of adequate veneration for specific ancestors, gods, and kings, as well as productive and plentiful harvest for the coming year.

Reference: Thanh, Phan. "Bảo Tồn Và Phát Huy Nét Đẹp Văn Hóa Truyền Thông Qua Lễ Tục Ew Muk Kei, Lễ Hội Katé-ramawan Và Lễ Hội Rija Nagar". In *Những Vấn Đề Văn Hóa-xã Hội Người Chăm Ngày Nay*, 5-31.. Tp. Hồ Chí Minh: Nxb. Trẻ, 2014.

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the purpose of the ritual to cause a change?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the change expected to be positive:

– Yes

Notes: Positive in the sense of improved spiritual balance once negative or harmful things are dispelled by ritual practitioners.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the change expected to be negative:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the change expected to be neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Select the type of change:

– Cultural

– Spiritual

– Ecological

Notes: + Communal

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

What is the domain involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it divine/spiritual:

– Yes

Notes: A central aspect of Rija Nagar is the connection between the community and the spirit realm. The Ka-ing spirit-medium priest functions as the liaison between these two domains, and is charged with expressing the wishes of both to one another. At times, during ceremonial dance and spirit possession, the Ka-ing will embody specific deities and relay their wishes to the community to conduct specific acts to cleanse the village and preserve its spiritual sanctity.

↳ Is it non-human organic entities (e.g., nature, animals, plants):

– Yes

Notes: Rija Nagar is deeply connected to nature, from the tone of the thunder storms at the beginning of the rainy season that signal its beginning, to the intended benefits of the ritual itself, which help to ensure rich and abundant crop productivity. Non-human animals play a central role at various parts of Rija Nagar events, such as the sacrificial offering of chicken on the first day, and the sacrificial offering of goat on the second day.

↳ Is it abiotic/inorganic entities (and objects):

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual participants are central to Rija Nagar, principally those of the Cham ancestral gods like Po Klaong Girai and Po Romé.

↳ Is it ecological:

– Yes

Notes: Yes Rija Nagar is deeply ecological as mentioned above, whose boundaries are demarcated by the changing dry season into a monsoon time period, the rumble of the thundering storms that mark the beginning of the ritual event, and the intended ecological benefits for crop production in the region, which comes as a result of the successful performance of this ritual.

↳ Is it transformed humans:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, individuals and entire communities transformed in that they begin a new year cleansed of any harmful spiritual energy, and achieve a sense of balance for the coming year. In addition, ritual practitioners like the Ka-ing spirit-medium priest, or the Muk Rija spirit-medium dancer, will become transformed during ceremonies as they enter into spirit possession.

↳ Is it for knowledge transmission (e.g., oral storytelling):

– Yes

Notes: Various hymns and ceremonial songs found across Rija Nagar events will be based on the historical tales, biographies, and legends (Damnay, Dulikal, etc.) of Cham ancestral heroes. These are based on hand-written manuscripts that are preserved and circulate in the Cham community written in the Cham script, Akhar Thrah. The transmission of these written biographies becomes manifest in the ritual events of Rija Nagar, whose textual content is translated into various songs, dance, and prayer among ritual specialists.

↳ Other:

– N/A

Is there a specific goal(s) associated with this ritual?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is devotion a goal of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Each day of the Rija Nagar is dedicated to different types of gods and spiritual ancestors in Cham culture. The first day, for example, contains practices intended for the veneration of Islamic-inspired 'new gods' (yang biruw), such as Po Awluah, while the second day contains practices intended for the veneration of Brahminic-inspired 'old gods' (yang aklak), such as Po Klaong Girai. In addition, particular villages will venerate different ancestral figures based on the heritage of their community, such as Po Klaong Can being worshipped specifically in Palei Hamu Craok.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ For deceased humans:

– Yes

↳ For ancestors:

– Yes

↳ For non-human, organic entities:

– No

↳ For abiotic or inorganic entities:

– Yes

↳ Are they rocks and stones:

– No

↳ Is it water?

– Yes

Notes: Seasonal monsoon rains.

↳ Are they human-created objects:

– No

↳ Are they landscape features:

– Yes [specify]: Rains, Harvest Fields

↳ For divine/spiritual beings:

– Yes

↳ Are they high gods:

– Yes

Notes: High gods would include figures like Po Awluah or Po Yang.

↳ Are they mixed divine (high-god)/human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Mixed divine would include ancestral kings, venerated as gods, such as Po Klaong Girai and Po Romé.

↳ For transformed/self-cultivated humans:

– Yes

Notes: Transformed/self-cultivated humans would include venerating the spirits of village ancestors who had become religious specialists and ritual practitioners in their lifetime.

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is creation of a cultural product a goal of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is propitiation a goal of this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, in that spiritual ancestors, such as the Cham kings Po Romé or Po Klaong Girai, are venerated and appeased, so as to bestow their spiritual guidance and support for the Cham community throughout the upcoming year.

↳ Is domestication of agents a goal?

Definition: temporary or permanent transformation of an inimical or indifferent target into something beneficial for practitioners.

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to gain information?

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual ancestors will, through the Ka-ing spirit-medium priest, convey their assessments of the village, and determine which rituals or practices must be conducted in order to cleanse the landscape and ensure good fortune for the commune.

↳ About the future/past/present:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual-ancestral assessments of the village will focus on the present state of the village, and outline the steps that must be taken to ensure a productive future.

↳ General information:

– No

↳ About something specific:

– Yes [specify]: Spiritual needs, and rituals practices, which must be followed to appease

ancestors, gods, and kings.

↳ Is this ritual practiced for cosmic maintenance?

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced for ecological maintenance and/or stewardship?

– Yes

↳ To increase felt connection with the more-than-human world:

– No

↳ To acknowledge responsibility for environmental harm:

– No

↳ To channel shame into collective reparative action:

– No

↳ To try to influence a larger change in the community (e.g., environmental values, motivations, beliefs, emotions):

– Yes

Notes: Yes the larger change in the community has to do with the overall balance of their spiritual well-being, the ecological productivity of the landscape, and the improved relationship with the population and their ancestral spirits.

↳ To evoke moral outrage (towards ecological injustice):

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for self-transformation?

– Yes

↳ To become god-like:

– No

↳ To become immortal:

– No

↳ To achieve divine or superhuman attributes:

– No

Notes: Some ritual practitioners will develop supernatural abilities during the Rija Nagar ritual events, specifically when they enter spirit possession and embody specific ancestral entities, such as Po Nai.

↳ For salvation/liberation from the world:

– No

↳ For spiritual cleansing:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual cleansing is a central element of Rija Nagar ritual events. In particular, this type of cleansing is intended for the village as a whole, and in doing so, helps to ensure a positive and productive new year.

↳ To achieve moral perfection:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritual morality is achieved through the proper implementation of Rija Nagar rituals. Particularly, the proper veneration of ancestral spirits, gods, and kings.

↳ For an initiation into a new status:

– No

↳ To achieve a change in mental state:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced as a way to express gratitude to a god or other supernatural

agents?

– Yes

Notes: Expressions of gratitude are central to many Rija Nagar ritual events, specifically those that are directed towards individual gods, kings, and village ancestors. For example, in venerating Po Romé, Sakaya (2003) recounts a specific hymn that states: "We are humble commoners. Please kneel and invite the deity Po Romé. Raise the voice inviting you to come. Water to wash the feet, sit at the ancestral altar. You ascend to the sky to text miraculous powers. Lord Po Romé is truly talented. You built damns and blocked rivers. Piled stones on mountains to make temples." (2003:79). This particular example of veneration recognizes not only the important place of Po Romé in Cham history, but also many of the specific contributions that Po Romé made towards the development of the Champa culture. Specifically, engineering expertise in the areas of irrigation and temple construction, which are widely recognized as highly developed in Cham civilization, are attributed to this Cham king, and these ritual hymns aim to recognize and express gratitude towards Po Romé for making such meaningful contributions.

Reference: Sakaya. *Lễ Hội Của Người Chăm*. Nhà xuất bản Văn hóa dân tộc, 2003.

↳ Is this ritual performed for purification?

– Yes

↳ Is it physical:

– Yes

↳ Is it mental:

– Yes

↳ Is it emotional:

– Yes

↳ Other:

–Specify: Spiritual, Communal

Notes: Purification from Rija Nagar extends to each of these listed categories (physical, mental, and emotional), as well as in other important areas like spiritual purification (in the expulsion of evil), and communal purification (in the cleansing of the entire village).

↳ Is this ritual practiced for exorcism purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for health/healing purposes?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to transmit information?

– Yes

Notes: While not an explicit element of Rija Nagar, the re-telling of historical biographies for ancient figures, such as the Cham kings Po Romé or Po Klaong Girai, are embedded in hymns and devotional music during the two-day event. In this way, folklore traditions are transmitted by ritual practitioners to other participants and observers from the community. At a different scale, information is transmitted between the spiritual realm and the local community by means of ritual practitioners like the Ka-ing spirit-medium priest. This exchange of information is crucial for the community to express their wishes to divine beings, and to receive instruction, based on those wishes, to have such aspirations for the new year come to fruition.

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain luck (generic)?

– Yes

Notes: Good luck and prosperity is desired among the village with respect to harvest production, as well as on an individual-basis for good fortune in the coming year.

↳ Is this a naming ritual?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to improve the community's modes of subsistence?

– Yes

Notes: Community participants in Rija Nagar will express desires for success in all forms of food-production, subsistence, and economic activity. As south-central Vietnam is largely centered around the agricultural industries for rice production, this will be a central desire for many during Rija Nagar. Nevertheless, as diverse industries continue to develop throughout Vietnam, people will express their desires for a productive year in any industry (from agricultural to industrial) that they, their families, or their village community members are a participant within.

↳ To increase the amount of rain for agricultural/horticultural productivity:

– Yes

↳ For crop success:

– Yes

↳ For livestock success:

– Yes

↳ For success in gathering:

– Yes

↳ For success in fishing:

– Yes

↳ For success in hunting:

– Yes

↳ For industrial productivity:

– Yes

↳ For success in commerce/mercantilism/market exchange:

– Yes

↳ Is this ritual practiced to induce harm?

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced for protection purposes?

– Yes

Notes: Rija Nagar wishes for good fortune in the coming year will involve protection from any

threat encountered in everyday life. This can range from physical harm in social contexts, to spiritual harm by means of harmful energy, witchcraft, or spells that surround an individual, family, or village.

↳ Against spells/witchcraft:
– Yes

↳ To avoid illness:
– Yes

↳ To avoid injury:
– Yes

↳ For a safe pregnancy:
– Yes

↳ For children:
– Yes

↳ To avoid discovery:
– Yes

↳ Against weapons:
– Yes

↳ To avoid vices (temptation):
– Yes

↳ Is this ritual associated with warfare or ritual contests (e.g., stick ball games)?
– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with craft practices (e.g., weaving, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: Traditional craft practices are among the most well-known aspects of Cham culture and civilization today. For example, Palei Hamu Craok is a famous pottery village, which is among the oldest in mainland Southeast Asia, and has been recognized by UNESCO under their list of Intangible Cultural Heritage in Need of Urgent Safeguarding. Palei Caklaing, likewise, is a famous brocade village, whose hand-woven style of textiles have become iconic with Cham identity in this region of Vietnam. Accordingly, many of these well-known craft practices will be present, to different degrees, during Rija Nagar ritual events across different villages, either by circumstance (in that they are a part of everyday life) or explicitly (as part of the ritual itself). For example, Muk Rija spirit-medium dancers may be adorned with simple white clothing during their spirit possession, which were produced using traditional Cham textile looms by hand. These textile traditions are a central element of many Cham legends, histories, and ancestral biographies, such as the Mother Goddess Po Inâ Nagar who taught weaving practices to the Cham people. Her contributions, in this regard, may be recognized during specific veneration of Po Inâ Nagar within villages where she is a central ancestral figure. Taken together, the craft practices that are associated with Cham heritage in Vietnam may be understood as a central element of nearly all ritual practice to some degree, and are especially salient in ceremonies dedicated to the ancestors, spirits, and gods that bestowed these abilities on the Cham civilization throughout history.

↳ Is this ritual associated with infanticide?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with gambling/games of chance?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with travel?

– No

↳ Is this ritual associated with social relations?

– Yes

Notes: Social relations also extend to the community relationships with specific ancestral spirits, gods, and kings.

↳ As part of a celebration:

– No

↳ For love:

– No

↳ For social coordination:

– Yes

Notes: Social coordination in the proper veneration of Cham ancestral spirits, gods, and kings among Cham villages.

↳ To reduce social discord:

– Yes

↳ To maintain partner faithfulness:

– No

↳ To cause religious conversion:

– No

↳ To obtain subjugation/control:

– No

↳ Is this ritual practiced to obtain wealth or success?

– No

Is the causal efficacy assessed?

– Yes

↳ Concrete outcomes in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The efficacy of Rija Nagar will be evident in the quality of seasonal harvests throughout the year. Abundant rain with rich yields helps to demonstrate the efficacy of Rija Nagar at the start of the year.

↳ Further ritual checks:

– No

Notes: While there are not specific "checks" to gauge the quality of Rija Nagar, subsequent rituals, and especially the other three Rija events, will have complimentary intentions of maintaining cosmological balance between village communities and ancestral spirits.

↳ Other:

– N/A

Techniques

Is sound practiced during this ritual?

– Yes

Is it considered "music" in the local culture/community?

– Yes

Is this sound coordinated with movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it oral?

– Yes

↳ Is it communal? (e.g., choir)

– Yes

↳ Is it individual?

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a call and response?
 - Yes
- ↳ It involves singing:
 - Yes
- ↳ It involves chanting:
 - Yes
- ↳ it involves invocation/prayer:
 - Yes
- ↳ It involves mantras:
 - Yes
- ↳ It involves wailing/cheering (heightened emotional expression):
 - Yes
- ↳ It involves narrative/recitation:
 - Yes
- ↳ It involves whistling:
 - Yes
- ↳ It involves shouting/loud vocalizations:
 - Yes
- ↳ How many individuals are involved in creating the vocalizations?
 - Yes

↳ Is the sound scripted?

– Yes

↳ Is the sound semantic?

– Yes

↳ How many languages are used in the ritual?

– Specify: 1

↳ Which language(s) are used in the ritual?

– Specify: Cham

Notes: Both written and spoken.

↳ Is the language(s) confined to the ritual:

– No

↳ Is it esoteric ritual language:

– No

↳ Is it esoteric divine language (i.e., speaking in tongues):

– No

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– Yes

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– Yes

↳ Is it specifically carried out by ritual specialists?

– Yes

- ↳ Does it require formal training?
 - Yes

- ↳ Do the vocalizations change throughout the ritual?
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is the change in vocalization correlated to the stage(s) of the ritual?
 - Yes

- ↳ Is there musical texture in the loud vocalizations?
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it homophonic:
 - No

 - ↳ Is it monophonic:
 - No

 - ↳ Is it polyphonic:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it heterophonic:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Is it biphonic:
 - No

- ↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by pitch?
 - Yes

↳ Are they codified?

– Yes

↳ Are the vocalizations regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Do they have a pulse?

– Yes

↳ Do they involve codified patterns?

– Yes

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Specify: Calibrated according to the performance of instruments, such as the kanyi.

↳ Are the vocalizations considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Fixed

Notes: See attached media files for examples.

↳ Is the sound produced with parts of the body?

– No

↳ Are there instruments/objects involved in creating sounds for the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they membranophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating a membrane (e.g., kettle drums, cylindrical drums).

— Yes

Notes: The two primary membranophone instruments in Rija Nagar are the Baranâng (single-sided drum), and the Gineng (dual-sided drum). Both of these play a central role in ritual events, for example, where the Maduen musical-specialist priest plays the Baranâng drum as the Ka-ing spirit-medium priest performs a dance and undergoes spirit possession. Likewise, the Gineng drums will be operated by two individuals, each with their own Gineng drum. These drummers will sit, cross-legged, facing one another, with their respective Gineng drums crossed in an X-like orientation. Using either small wooden drum sticks or their open hands, they will play in unison alongside other musicians (such as those playing the Baranâng and Saranai) as ritual specialists, such as the Ka-ing of Muk Rija, conduct dances, make ceremonial offerings, and experience spiritual possession. An example of both of these instruments being performed can be seen in Media File [6] of this database entry, where the ensemble of musicians perform for the Muk Rija entering her spirit-possession trance.

↳ Are they idiophone:

Definition: Instruments that create sound through vibrating themselves (e.g., xylophones, jaw's harp).

— No

↳ Are they aerophone:

Definition: Instruments that create noise by pushing vibrating columns of air through them (e.g., accordions, pitch pipes, ocarinas, bagpipes).

— Yes

Notes: The primary aerophone instrument in Rija Nagar ritual practices is the Saranai, a small, high-pitched, trumpet-flute horn instrument. The distinctive sound of the Saranai has become associated with many Cham cultural practices, ritual events, and heritage festivals today. In the context of Rija Nagar, this instrument plays an important role in accompanying the Ka-ing spirit medium priest, as well as other Maduen priests (playing the Baranâng and Gineng drums), during ritual events where offerings are made, dances are performed, and ritual specialists communicate with the spiritual realm. An example of Saranai performance can be seen and heard in Media File [9] of this database entry.

↳ Are they chordophone:

Definition: Instruments that produce sound by vibrating strings (e.g., guitar, violin, harp).

– Yes

Notes: The primary chordophone instrument found in Rija Nagar ritual events is the Kanyi, a two-stringed instrument played with a bow. Maduen priests will play this instrument alongside Baranâng drums as they recite sacred hymns. An example of this instrument being performed can be seen in Media File [2] of this database entry, depicting the veneration of Po Klaong Can at Palei Hamu Craok.

↳ Are they electrophone:

Definition: Instruments where the sound is produced by electric or electronic means (e.g., synthesizers, computers).

– No

↳ Are they architectural features:

def: water channeled in underground canals, fountains, or other architectural features that create sounds for the ritual

– No

↳ How many individuals are involved in producing these instrumental sounds:

– Yes

Notes: Each instrument will have a respective specialist performing them during Rija Nagar ritual events. In general, there will be at least 3 maduen priests playing drums (either in a 3-person ensemble of baranâng, or in an ensemble of one baranâng and two gineng), as well as a maduen to play the kanyi or saranai.

↳ Is it scripted?

– Yes

Notes: Classical hymns and musical notation for Cham musical performances are recorded in hand-written manuscripts that are kept in the Cham community.

↳ Is it semantic?

– No

↳ Is it mimetic (of non-human animal, natural, human)?

– No

↳ Is it restricted to ritual use?

– No

Notes: The instruments themselves are not restricted to ritual use, as they are often featured in cultural-heritage events and festivals.

↳ Is it performed by specialists?

– Yes

↳ Does it require formal training?

– Yes

↳ Does the sound change throughout the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Does the change correlate to the stage of the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Pace and rhythm may change according to the stage of different ritual events.

↳ Is there musical texture in the instrumental sound?

– Yes

↳ Is it homophonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it monophonic:

– No

↳ Is it polyphonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it heterophonic:

– Yes

↳ Is it biphonic:

– Yes

↳ Is the sound regulated by pitch?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve codified patterns?

– Yes

↳ Is the sound regulated by rhythm?

– Yes

↳ Is there a pulse?

– Yes

↳ Codified/non-codified patterns

– Yes

↳ The pace of the rhythm is:

– Yes

Notes: Varied based on the specific ritual being performed during Rija Nagar. See attached media files [2], [6], and [9] for examples.

↳ Is the sound considered central to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ The sound is:

– Semi-improvised

Notes: Each song will follow specific formulas based on the structure of the hymns or songs being performed, but the specific pace of the rhythm may increase depending on the portion of the ritual, such as increasing tempos during the climax of spiritual possession.

Is movement involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it considered "dance" by the culture that practices this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The Rija system in Cham culture is sometimes described as a series of seasonal dance festivals. Accordingly, the specific dances that happen during this two-day event are a centerpiece of the ritual event. The Ka-ing priest will have separate dances for different deities invited to attend ceremonial events. In all cases, he will dance to the sound of the baranâng, gineng, and saranai as ceremonial offerings are made. Dances will often be accompanied by recitation of sacred hymns, which are chanted by Maduen (drum) and Kadhar (fiddle) priests. As the hymns are sung, the Ka-ing will hold the ceremonial whip and dance following the rhythm of the drum and the cries of the audience in attendance. As this continues, the Ka-ing will enter into a trance, and at its climax, will hold the horse whip and stamp out a blazing fire on the ground (symbolizing heat and draught) amid cheers from the crowd. This specific dance is perhaps the most iconic and well-known dance practice for Rija Nagar ritual events, and has the function of bringing favorable rain and wind for the coming year.

Reference: Truong, Van Mon. "Hệ Thống Lễ Raja Champa". In Văn Hóa - Lịch Sử Champa [III]: Mối Quan Hệ Giữa Champa Và Thế Giới Mã Lai. Nhà Xuất bản ĐH Quốc Gia TP.HCM, 2024.

↳ Is it coordinated with sound?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve the use of objects?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals are involved in this movement

– Specify: 1 to 2

↳ Do actors move in close proximity to each other?

– Yes

↳ Do actors move towards each other?

– Yes

↳ Do actors move away from each other?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve ritualized action?

– Yes

↳ It involves kneeling:

– Yes

↳ It involves prostrating:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve remaining immobile:

– No

↳ Does it involve artistic movement (e.g., mandala)?

– Yes

↳ Is it mimetic (natural, non-human world)?

– No

↳ Does it involve a symbolic representation?

– Yes

↳ Does it include stereotyped/stylized movements?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve a procession?

– No

↳ Does it involve a pilgrimage?

– No

↳ Are there gestures involved in the movement?

– Yes

↳ Are there particular postures involved in the movement?

– Yes

↳ Is it choreographed?

– No

↳ Is it a narrative?

– Yes

↳ Is it restricted to the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it involuntary? (caused by trance, etc.)

– Yes

↳ Is there a specific proximity considered between individuals while moving?

– No

Is there regalia/ornamentation used as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific body markings done for the ritual?

– No

↳ Is there hair regulation as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Is there tooth modification involved in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are individuals partly or fully naked as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are scars made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Are piercings made as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Does genital modification take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Do individuals have to wear specific clothing for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are there specific shoes to be worn for this ritual?

– No

↳ Is there a head covering used during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it removed at some point during the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Ka-ing priests will wear different head-dresses during different parts of Rija Nagar ritual events.

↳ Is it added during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the clothing colors regulated for the ritual?

– Yes

Notes: The Ka-ing spirit-medium priest will wear red-colored robes during the ritual, while others, such as the Maduen, will be dressed in white.

↳ Are there specific clothing items restricted for exclusive use in the ritual?

– No

↳ Are there jewelry/charms used during this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are masks used during the ritual?

– No

Are there materials/objects used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they totems:

– No

↳ Are they religious icons:

– No

↳ Are they fetishes:

– No

↳ Are they vessels:

– No

↳ Are they masks:

– No

↳ Are they standards (banner, flag):

– No

↳ Other:

– Specify: The dance props include: 01 oar; 01 red sugarcane stalk (symbolizing a boat oar); 01 fan, cloth, and 01 horse whip. All props, except the cloth and fan, are held in the hand of the Ka-ing priest (the spirit-medium); the rest are placed at the ancestral altar (danaok). At the ancestral altar, where the offerings and dance props are placed, there is also an axe handle (a labor tool).

Notes: In addition to these particular ceremonial objects used during Rija Nagar dances, there are also specific objects that are central to the completion of Rija Nagar on the second day. The Salih is a substitute effigy made from raw rice flower depicting two men and two women. The second (leaving) day of Rija Nagar is concluded when this effigy is carried out of the ritual space by the Maduen priest and the Ka-ing priest, and then sent away down a river or at a three-way cross-roads of the village. This effigy represents a stand-in for the villagers themselves, and its departure signifies the sending away of drought, heat, and unlucky fortune of the old year, and welcoming abundant rain, strong winds, and plentiful harvests. The completion of this specific ritual signifies the official closing and end of Rija Nagar for the year.

Reference: Truong, Van Mon. "Hệ Thống Lễ Raja Champa". In Văn Hóa - Lịch Sử Champa [III]: Mỗi Quan Hệ Giữa Champa Và Thế Giới Mã Lai. Nhà Xuất bản ĐH Quốc Gia TP.HCM, 2024.

↳ How are these materials/objects implemented?

– Yes

↳ Are they sound-producing:

– Yes

Notes: The musical instruments utilized in Rija Nagar include the high-pitched saranai trumpet, two types of membranophonic instruments: dual-sided low-tone gineng drums, and the smaller, baranâng drums, and a chordophone instrument, the kanyi. For examples of these instruments being utilized during Rija Nagar ritual events, see attached media files [2], [6], and [9] of this database entry. For news coverage about the production of these specific types of drums, see the 2019 feature story in Vietnam Today entitled, "The Art of Making Cham Drums (part 3/3) | VTV World" <https://youtu.be/aMrd1iXJw?si=YRryqz34q6xuVICU>

↳ Are they divination tools:

– Yes

Notes: The ensemble of trumpets and drums are a central motif in leading the spirit-possession ceremonies.

↳ Are they drug paraphenalia:

– No

↳ Are they cutting devices:

– No

↳ Are they sceptres/wands:

– No

↳ Is text used during this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it a diagram:

– No

↳ Is it an inscribed item:

– No

↳ Is it a book:

– Yes

Notes: Ritual practitioners may reference hand-written Cham manuscripts during events that contain sacred hymns and musical notation.

↳ Is it a scroll:

– No

↳ Is it a tablet:

– No

↳ Is it memorized text:

– Yes

Notes: Religious dignitaries like the Maduen musicians may have already memorized hymns and ritual prayers during Rija Nagar ritual events.

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Is painting used during the ritual?

– No

↳ Is a technological object used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are plants or plant parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Various plants are utilized in different ritual offerings during Rija Nagar, such as betel nuts.

↳ Are animals or animal parts used in this ritual?

– Yes

Notes: Chicken sacrifices are made on the first (entering) day of Rija Nagar, while goat sacrifices are made on the second (leaving) day of Rija Nagar. In addition, other animal products like eggs will be part of sacrifice, prayers, and other ceremonial events.

↳ Are human body parts (including flesh) used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Are bodily fluids used as part of this ritual?

– No

↳ Do topical applications take place during this ritual?

– No

↳ Is water used?

– Yes

↳ Is earth used?

– No

↳ Is a mirror used?

– No

↳ Are textiles used?

– Yes

Notes: Traditional textiles are found throughout Rija Nagar ritual events, such as the white cloth adorning the kajang that symbolizes the universe, or the traditional clothing textiles worn by ritual

specialists during Rija Nagar.

↳ Is fire used?

– Yes

Notes: During Rija Nagar, the Ka-ing spirit-medium priest will light a small fire on the ground that symbolizes the hot dry season. As musicians play, the Ka-ing will dance and enter into a trance of spirit possession. As this experience continues, they will dance more intensely, and eventually stamp out the small fire with their bare feet. This act signals the changing of the seasons, leaving behind the dry season, and welcoming the wet rainy season at the beginning of the new year.

↳ Is it smoke:

– Yes

↳ Is it incense:

– No

↳ Is it candle(s):

– No

↳ Is it torch(es):

– No

↳ Is it burnt objects like paper, leaves, or wood:

– Yes

↳ Is it a large fire:

– No

↳ Is there interaction with ritual material during the ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it passed around?

– No

↳ Is it kissed?

– No

↳ Is it placed somewhere specifically?

– Yes

Notes: Ritual offerings (like food and wine) will be placed on the danaok (ceremonial alter) alongside other symbolic objects like an axe handle (symbolizing labor). In total, there will be five trays of rice, soup, cakes, fruits, betel, and local rice wine (alak).

↳ Is it processed to create something else?

– No

↳ Is it touched?

– Yes

↳ Is it used to touch?

– Yes

↳ Is it altered during the course of the ritual?

– No

↳ Is it worn?

– No

↳ Is it used to maintain a boundary?

– No

↳ Is it placed at a specific physical distance?

– No

Does consumption take place as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ How many individuals participate in consumption?

– Specify: 10

Notes: Varies, depending on how many community members attend consumption portions of ritual events.

↳ Is food consumed?

– Yes

Notes: Food consumption will take place following the conclusion of ritual events. This portion of Rija Nagar is not a formal aspect or portion of the ritual itself, but will generally happen where religious dignitaries eat together, and community members in the village eat together.

↳ Is it human:

Definition: this can include by fire, natural features of landscape

– No

↳ Is it a non-human animal:

– Yes

↳ Is it a plant:

– Yes

↳ Is it a fungus:

– No

↳ Is this food restricted to the ritual?

– No

↳ Is the preparation of the food ritualized?

– No

↳ Is the presentation of the food ritualized?

– Yes

↳ In what state is the food consumed?

– Cooked

↳ Is a non-normative portion (excessive or deficient) served?

– Yes

↳ Is it sacralized food?

– Yes

↳ Is it symbolic food?

e.g., standing in for another food or substance or metaphysical concept

– Yes

↳ Is the food consumed associated with healing powers?

– No

↳ Does food consumption happen on site?

– Yes

↳ Does the food consumption happen off site?

– Yes

↳ Does the ritual take place before food consumption?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the supernatural source of the food?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the environmental source of the food?

– Yes

↳ Is there an acknowledgement of the (human) provider of the food?

– Yes

↳ Does the ritual encourage sustainable eating behavior?

– No

↳ Are there specific types of consumption that are forbidden?

– Yes

Notes: Consumption of prohibited foods includes those that are generally not eaten by certain religious groups of the Cham community, such as beef among Cham Ahiér, or pork among Cham Awal.

↳ Is a psychoactive substance used in this ritual?

– No

↳ How is the substance used in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Is it smoked:

– No

↳ Is it ingested:

– No

↳ Is it applied topically:

– No

↳ Is it chewed:

– No

↳ Is it a suppository:

– No

↳ Is it snorted:

– No

↳ Is it injected:

– No

↳ Is it offered into the fire:

– No

↳ Is it offered to non-human animals or natural features:

– No

↳ Does it require fasting beforehand:

– No

↳ Does it cause vomiting:

– No

↳ Are other substances used in this ritual?

– No

↳ Is the substance shared from a communal vessel or implement?

– Yes

Notes: Food may be consumed communally from a salao, a circular aluminum tray for serving food.

Does the ritual stimulate an altered state of consciousness?

– Yes

↳ Does the individual retain biographical identity?

– Yes

Notes: The Ka-ing may embody spirits or gods during portions of Rija Nagar ritual events, but they will not lose their identity as the Ka-ing spirit-medium priest.

↳ Does the individual retain control of the body?

– No

↳ Does a spirit possession take place?

– Yes

↳ Is it named:

– Yes

↳ Is it recognized by the community:

– Yes

↳ Does it cause the individual to speak in an incomprehensible language?

– No

↳ Does it generate super-strength?

– No

↳ Does it lead to a prophecy/clairvoyance?

– Yes

Notes: Spirit possession for the Ka-ing will help to relay community desires (eg. for abundant rain) to the spiritual realm, and vice-versa. Importantly, this exchange will dictate, from spirits to the community, the proper practices that need to be followed to cleans the village, appease the spirits, and grant them their aspirations for the new year.

↳ Does it create an extra-human resilience/resistance to harm?

– No

↳ Does it help an individual to gain other new abilities or properties?

– No

↳ Does it involve spirit travel?

– Yes

↳ Where does the spirit travel to?

–Specify: Spirits enter the village and/or ritual areas from the east.

↳ Is the individual chosen (e.g., by a supernatural agent)?

– No

↳ Is there a method of induction?

– No

Are offerings involved as part of this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings non-material?

– No

↳ Are the offerings material?

– Yes

↳ Are they consumed by the ritual participants?

– Yes

↳ Are the offerings symbolic?

– Yes

↳ Is there a substitution used to represent the symbolic offerings?

– No

↳ Do offerings serve as payments for the ritual specialists?

– No

↳ Are animals offered?

– Yes

↳ Is the whole animal offered?

– Yes

↳ How many animals are offered?

– Specify: 1

↳ Is part of the animal offered?

– No

↳ Are the animals domestic?

– Yes

↳ How many domestic?

– Specify: 1

↳ Are they wild animals?

– No

↳ Are humans offered?

– No

↳ Is food offered for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are specific drinks offered for this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are psychoactive substances offered?

– Yes

Notes: Betel

↳ Are commodities offered?

– Yes

↳ Are household items offered?

– No

↳ Are personal items offered?

– No

↳ Is clothing offered?

– No

↳ Are musical instrument offered?

– No

↳ Are texts offered?

– No

↳ Are weapons offered?

– No

↳ Is money (or other valuable items) offered?

– No

↳ Are precious substances offered?

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

Are non-normative practices involved in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are they self-imposed?

– Yes

↳ Are they other-imposed?

– No

↳ Does it involve fasting?

– No

↳ Does it involve sensory deprivation?

– No

↳ Does it involve submersion in water?

– No

↳ Does it involve being in a difficult bodily position?

– No

↳ Does it involve the consumption of disgusting substances?

– No

↳ Does it involve sleep deprivation?

– No

↳ Does it involve physical exhaustion?

– Yes

Notes: Physical exhaustion is generally a part of spirit-possession portions of Rija Nagar ritual events, such as at the conclusion of Muk Rija spirit-possession dances.

↳ Does it involve physical discomfort?

– No

↳ Does it involve excessive labor?

– No

↳ Does it involve psychological discomfort?

– No

↳ Does it involve physical pain?

– No

↳ Does it involve positive emotion?

– Yes

↳ It involves ecstasy:

– Yes

↳ It involves joy:

– Yes

↳ It involves love:

– No

↳ It involves feelings of connection:

– Yes

Notes: Connection between ritual specialists, as well as the community at-large, with the spiritual realm.

↳ It involves pride:

– Yes

↳ It involves hope:

– Yes

Notes: Hope for a prosperous new year, with good fortune, abundant rain, and plentiful crops.

↳ It involves gratitude:

– Yes

Notes: Gratitude towards spirits, ancestors, kings, and gods.

↳ It involves awe:

– Yes

↳ It involves compassion/empathy:

– No

↳ It involves equanimity:

– No

↳ Other:

– N/A

↳ Does it involve negative emotion?

– No

↳ Does it involve breath manipulation?

– No

↳ Does it involve a vow of silence?

– No

↳ Does it involve the subversion of social categories?

– No

↳ Does it involve non-normative sexual acts?

– No

↳ Does it involve celibacy?

– No

Formal Features

Does the ritual stand by itself?

– No

Notes: Rija Nagar is one of four different Rija events throughout the year. Importantly, Rija Nagar is comprised of many different, specific, ritual ceremonies and practices over a two-day period. Many of these are found among all Rija Nagar events in all Cham villages, while further variations can be found within villages that pertain to the veneration of specific deities, ancestors, kings, and other famous figures from the history of the Champa civilization.

Is the ritual part of a sequence of rituals?

– Yes

Is the repetition of the ritual determinate (e.g., an action must be repeated a certain number of times)?

– Yes

Notes: This varies depending on the particular practice at different points of the two-day Rija Nagar, as well as further variations depending on local village-level traditions venerating certain ancestors and gods.

Is the repetition of the ritual non-determinate?

– No

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of repetition?

– Low

Compared to everyday non-ritual behavior, what is the level of rigidity of this ritual?

– Medium

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of arousal of this ritual?

– High

Compared to everyday non-ritual activity, what is the level of physical activity in this ritual?

– Medium

Is there behavioral conformity?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of behavioral conformity
– High

Is there synchrony in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ Are the roles differentiated?
– Yes

Is there entrainment in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of entrainment?
– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?
– Yes

↳ Is the entrainment emerging endogenously between participants in the ritual?
(e.g., clapping, chanting without external stimulus)
– Yes

↳ Is the entrainment to an external stimulus?

(e.g., a ritual leader, a musical beat)

– Yes

↳ Does the entrainment induce emotional conformity?

– Yes

Is there coordination in this ritual?

– Yes

↳ What is the level of coordination?

– High

↳ Is there movement/sound/attention?

– Yes

Is there preparation time needed to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

How many hours are involved in the ritual preparation?

– Specify: 48

Are there preparation activities involved?

– Yes

↳ Does it involve fasting:

– No

↳ Does it involve purification:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve learning/training:

– Yes

↳ Does it involve penance:

– No

↳ Does it involve abstention:

– No

Is practice/expertise required to carry out this ritual?

– Yes

What is the level of expertise required?

– High

What is the level of economic cost involved to practice this ritual?

– Yes

↳ In local currency:

– Specify: VND

↳ Number of people or days of labor equivalent:

– Specify: 30

↳ Other measure of cost:

– N/A

What is the transmission mode of the ritual?

– Many-many

How is the ritual transmitted?

- In oral form
- Artistic representation
- Other:: Performance, Ritual Prayer, Offerings

Who or what has authority over this ritual?

- Divine beings
- Sagely human
- Religious specialists
- Social

Bibliography

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